

Increasing Communication Skills of Community Care Hospice Nurses

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Background

- In 2017, 20.4 million people worldwide were diagnosed with life-limiting illnesses
- Quality of care is the primary focus at end of life (EOL) in both hospice and palliative care settings
- 80% of Americans prefer to die at home
 - 25% of deaths occur at home
- Effective communication is a key clinical element in quality hospice/palliative care
- Research supports the use of the EOL Nursing and Education Consortium (ELNEC) COMFORT communication curriculum for EOL education
- ELNEC /COMFORT training based on evidence & provides reliable & valid education

Purpose

To implement and evaluate a communication educational program for hospice nurses at a Community Care Hospice (CCH).

Method

Design

- Quality improvement using the PDSA model with pre and post-testing
- Involved adoption and implementation of the ELNEC Communication Module Six, along with the COMFORT^{TMSM} curriculum

Sample

- Nine CCH nursing participants

Setting

- CCH Facility located in Southern California

Measures

- Demographic: self-Report Questionnaire before teaching session
- Nurses Knowledge of EOL: Pre & Post 13 item Questionnaire (used from ELNEC)
- Nurses' Self-Efficacy: Pre & Post 10 items survey (used from ELNEC)
- Evaluation of Communication: 7 items Post program

Intervention

- EOL communication content training from ELNEC Module 6 and COMFORT^{TMSM} curriculum
- Two-hour face to face training sessions, every two weeks for one months (Total of 2 sessions)

PDSA Model for Quality Improvement

Results

Means of Pre and Posttest Knowledge Percent Scores

Means of Pre and Post tests Self-efficacy Scores

Summary of Program Evaluation Scores

Variable	M	SD	n
Total	27.56	3.0	9

Reliability Table for Score

No of items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
7	0.79	0.62	0.96

Note: The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95% confidence interval.

Discussion

Demand for EOL care continues to increase

- Knowledgeable and competent nurses
- Flexible and fluid in communication about EOL

Role of Hospice Nurses created need

- Training in communication skills
- ELNEC communication Module 6 and COMFORT communication added to the education program

Effective improvement in nurses' knowledge and self-efficacy in communication

- Pre-post questionnaires and self-efficacy survey showed improvement in knowledge and self-efficacy (Glover et al., 2017; Malloy, 2010).
- Same pre/post tools used in this project - showed improvement and reliability of the training.

Nurses' reflection on narratives

- Identified communication concerns at EOL
- Many were satisfied after training.

Limitation

COVID-19 pandemic –

- Uncertainty due to lockdown
- Nurse's availability in visiting patients difficult

Educational training

- Shortened from four one-hour session to two-two-hour session

Implication and Conclusion

- Implementing ELNEC/ COMFORT communication training was a useful teaching modality for hospice nurses
- Training was successful, improved nurses' knowledge of EOL care with statistical significance.
- Project demonstrated need for skills-based learning such as role play
- Mindful communication and active listening is vital in EOL care
- Future training with ELNEC/COMFORT was recommended.
- ANA/HPNA (2017) endorsed ELNEC and COMFORT training for all nursing levels
- Use of these modules as the standard palliative curriculum.